

**ACTIVE LEARNING METHODS IN ENGLISH LESSONS AS A MEANS
OF INCREASING THE QUALITY OF LEARNING**

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Annotation: the article deals with a great difference of methods of educating foreign languages to young generations namely pupils. Each teaching method is mainly based on a particular vision of comprehension the language or the learning process, frequently using specific techniques and materials used in a set sequence.

Keywords: method, specific techniques, games, communication, student, teacher, pupil, interactive, vocabulary, form of training.

Each teaching method is mainly based on a particular vision of comprehension the language or the learning process, frequently using specific techniques and materials used in a set sequence. Language teachers who deeply study and use various methods of teaching English are those who take care of their own value to self, to pupils, to family, to society and to a larger community of the world. Nowadays everything is changeful, particularly, in teaching the English language. In fact, there is a great difference of methods of educating foreign languages to young generations namely pupils. Diverse ways of educating English can be both demanding and challenging for teachers along with pupils, they can also be tremendously stimulating and rewarding.

It is universally accepted that language teaching of pupils is the most complicated process. Due to the fact that current young language learners are big fan of learning several items or subjects, such as utilizing the computer, the mobile phone and so on. In this case, teachers ought to aware of pupil's interests and possibilities. Namely, the objective of the foreign language lessons in primary schools is to develop learner's skills in understanding English speech and

participating in conversation based on the topics covered. We know, in education system interactive games are very important for teaching learners especially for learning foreign languages. Usually teachers use a lot of interactive games during the lessons. So, students like this way of teaching lessons too. Thus, teachers need to keep modifying their lessons to fit this type of learners. While games are thought to be fun and benefit learners in various ways, games have become the most suitable activities for children.

However, since teachers are solely responsible in making decisions what to teach in class, it is the best to explore the teacher's points of view on games as learning activities. Therefore, the research objectives of this study focus on teacher's primary purpose of using games, their perception on the effectiveness of games as teaching tools and the criteria considered by teachers when choosing games to use in young children classes. These games especially will be effective for learning languages. Every teacher should know interactive games how to effect to children. Teachers should plan the lessons with the true way, since learning is invariably changing, teachers don't have any other choices but to keep modifying their teaching methods and approaches.

As a teacher of supplementing lesson plans in the classroom, he or she is often found to turn games. One of all the reasons would be a well demonstration of justification for using games in the classroom. Games are believed to benefit learners in a variety of ways ranging from the cognitive aspects of language learning to more co-operative group dynamics. In truth, every student wishes to play games purely for fun and nothing more than that. Different from the students, teachers strictly need appropriate and nothing more than that. Different from the students, teachers strictly need appropriate and convincing reasons before including games in their lecture. Teachers are believed to take times to consider a variety of things such as what type of games to use, when to use them appropriately, how to correctly link them with the language focus, the syllabus, textbook or even the program, as well as how different types of games will benefit the students in different ways. The further precise explanation on this fact is that teachers would spend time to 24 question

themselves which skills or sub-skills are to be improved by games the learner's status in the particular skill. If we speak about games we know there are a lot of interesting and active, easy games to use in lessons.

Games can be used as an ice-breaker or warm-up at the beginning of class, as an introduction activity for new vocabulary or grammar, as a review exercise at the end of a lesson, chapter or before an exam. If we are still uncertain of what to teach English learners you may want to use or how to go about making them work for our classroom, perhaps the following examples may help us. Then, scramble the vocabulary words so that the students must discover from each scrambled word the vocabulary to go letter-by-letter in the boxes behind it. The target word can then be placed in a vertical fashion using those letters from the vocabulary. I hope those ideas and suggestions on games to teach English learners have been helpful for you and that you can find a way to use them in your next class.

For example, memory games they feature the best ESL concentration games to help student's master English vocabulary and grammar. These vocabulary games help students develop good word recognition, listening, reading and spelling skills. So, I say in conclusion that interactive games are very useful, effective and easy to teach young children English language. Because every learner likes active games and want to spend the lessons with interesting games. Moreover, this way of teaching is used every country. So, every teacher should try to use interactive games in lessons.

New methods and requirements for foreign language teaching in the country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills.

Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in education is the ability of students to know and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most effective ways.

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